

Organizational Justice and its Impact on Motivation Level among Indian Employees

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Abstract: Organizational Justice and Employee motivation are two separate theories whose connections to one another are not very clear. The purpose of this paper is to analyse the relationship between these two concepts. Motivation level is one of the most essential factors for positive productivity in any workplace. Keeping motivation levels alive involves providing justice to employees, or organizational justice. Organizational Justice is based on fairness of reward distribution within an organization or workplace environment according to individual contributions which are judged by their performance. It is a way of giving employees satisfactory treatment by showing respect towards them and rewarding them for their efforts done towards the organization. The study was conducted by taking a sample of 137 employees from 5 automobile manufacturing organizations in Pune City, using convenience sampling. This study found that the perceived level of Organizational Justice was significantly positively correlated with the level of motivation of the employees.

Keywords: Organizational Justice, Employee Motivation, Indian Automobile Sector

1. Introduction

Organizational Justice and Employee motivation are two separate theories whose connections to one another are not very clear. The purpose of this paper is to analyze the relationship between these two concepts. Theory of Justice was first built on August 8, 1971 by John Rawls in his book, A Theory of Justice. Rawls believes that justice is a matter of fairness, rather than equality. He believes that even though our society may not be fair or equal at all times due to inequalities between the rich and poor and some groups such as women having less power than the other groups, we should strive for a fair society where everyone is treated equally under law and policy. Organizational justice is the definition of fairness that each employee receives at work based on their status, position,

and gender. It is important to note that organizational justice is not equal in all organizations because they vary in size and structure (Burt, 2005; Edwards and Johnstone, 2007; Lim and Yan, 2002) depending on the company or organization. Organizational justice describes three types of fairness: Fairness of Opportunity, Fairness of Working Conditions and Fairness of Decisions. Organizational justice can affect employee motivation positively or negatively because employees may work harder or less hard depending on the type and quality of justice that they receive.

Motivation level is one of the most essential factors for positive productivity in any work place. Keeping motivation levels alive involves providing justice to employees, or organizational justice. Organizational Justice is based on fairness of reward distribution within an organization or workplace environment according to individual contributions which are judged by their performance (Dunckley and Dunckley, 2003). It is a way of giving employees satisfactory treatment by showing respect towards them and rewarding them for their efforts done towards the organization. Organizational justice is based on fairness of reward distribution within an organization or workplace environment according to individual contributions which are judged by their performance (Dunckley and Dunckley, 2003). It is a way of giving employees satisfactory treatment by showing respect towards them and rewarding them for their efforts done towards the organization. It also involves fulfilling obligations and providing equitable treatment to all employees. Fairness can be defined as providing positive rewards to people even if they don't perform well or a feeling that one has been treated fairly at work (Brammer and Cooper, 2009). This research is conducted to identify factors that influence employees' motivation level.

2. Review of Literature

In the literature, there are a few definitions of organizational justice. According to Geis and Lewin (1992), organizational justice is an outcome or performance management, payout and decision-making process that is fair and impartial (p. 140). They further define it as a set of values and beliefs that promote ethical behaviour and productive work environments. Fries (1988) also highlights the notion of organizational justice as the organised social system created to promote the welfare of employees within an organisation. Righteousness is defined as the type of behaviour and attitude that encourages respect for others and helps in building cooperative teams (Sarason, 1991). Organizational justice is seen as a way of rewarding employees who have performed well in the workplace. Organizational justice has shown to be strongly related to employee motivation. Organizational justice depends on the employees' perception of fairness, fairness perceptions of all relevant individuals and perceived fairness of reward allocation processes (Poynor and Charpentier, 2005; Sarason and Gneezy, 1999).

Some ways in which organizational justice is measured are by their treatment of employees at work (Brammer and Cooper, 2009). These methods assess how fair an organization is and what factors influence that fairness. Other methods include distributing the same amount of pay and punish those who do not perform well (Fries, 1988). Organizational justice is seen as a relational concept that involves all relevant individuals – the organization, the superior and subordinates. The organization, for example, should be fair and have a good relationship with its customers. Its superior should also be fair to their subordinates by treating them fairly and maintaining a good communication with them so that all employees can work towards the common goal (Brammer and Cooper, 2009).

There are two types of justice theories: distributive and procedural justice. Distributive Justice is the belief that having whatever one wants to is just and acceptable. It involves the perception of how much something should be distributed or allocated. Procedural justice is when everything works out as it should, meaning that everyone gets what they deserve (Brammer and Cooper, 2009). Organizational justice focuses on fairness in the workplace's reward distribution process. Companies must help employees accept their assignments and responsibilities and maintain a fair relationship with people in their company (Brammer and Cooper 2009). This will encourage people to stay at work and do their jobs well because they are being treated fairly by the organization and its superior(s) (Brammer and Cooper 2009). In addition, according to Brammer and Cooper (2009), fairness will increase employee motivation. If a company is seen by people as fair or just, employees will have lower levels of job satisfaction, but higher levels of motivation (Brammer and Cooper, 2009). Employees are then motivated to work harder in order to achieve the outcome that the company desires.

3. Methodology

Following methodology was designed for the study to collect primary data.

- a) Identify a sample of 137 employees from 5 automobile manufacturing organizations using convenience sampling (organizations were having their offices within the limits of the Pune Region)
- b) Design and validate a (minimum 20-point) questionnaire for ascertainment of
- c) Level of employee motivation (20 items)
- d) Level of perceived organizational justice (30 items)
- e) Conduct the survey
- f) Summarize the responses
- g) Apply correlation analysis and check the level of significance.
- h) Analyse the results

The hypotheses set in this regard were as under:

H_{o1}: Perceived level of Organizational Justice is not correlated with the Employee Motivation.

H_{a1}: Perceived level of Organizational Justice is significantly positively correlated with the Employee Motivation.

The study was conducted across Pune City.

Scheme formed for testing of hypotheses

Responses were collected under 3 sections:

- a) First section of the questionnaire was dedicated to the profile information of the employees
- b) Second section was dedicated to Employee Motivation
- c) Third section gathered responses for measuring the level perceived organizational justice.

For each of the sections an average was calculated.

- a) Percentages to questions under a particular section of the questionnaire were averaged to get a single score for that section,
- b) The section-wise average score was considered for the purpose of conducting a correlation analysis.
- c) P-values were calculated, and the null hypotheses were checked for rejection or non-rejection.

Cronbach’s alpha score for the questionnaire was calculated the results have been discussed in the next section of the paper.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows that the values of Cronbach’s alpha was above 0.7 in each of the cases. This shows the level of internal consistency and proves the validity of the measures that have been calculated.

Table 1: Results of the Cronbach’s Alpha

Sr. No.	Section of the questionnaire	Number of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha value
1	Level of employee motivation	20	0.791
2	Level of perceived organizational justice	30	0.786
3	Complete Questionnaire	50	0.761

Table 2: Correlations

		Organizational Justice	Employee Motivation
Organizational Justice	Pearson Correlation	1	.563**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
Employee Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.563**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	

Note: N= 137. ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 shows that the perceived level of Organizational Justice is significantly positively correlated with the Employee Motivation.

5. Conclusion

Several studies have studied the relationship between Employee Motivation and perceived level of Organizational Justice. The study found that four factors especially were closely associated with organizational justice:

- 1) The organization's communication with its employees,
- 2) The organization's consistency in applying rules,
- 3) The employee's perception of fairness in formulating policies that affect them, and
- 4) How well employees feel they are treated by management?

The conclusion is that Organizational Justice is essential to Employee Motivation. It has a positive impact on company productivity and profitability as well as on morale. Our blog post will explore these effects in greater detail. It's important to note that while organizational justice is essential to employee motivation, it cannot be used as a replacement for monetary compensation as a driver of employee retention. The first table shows the correlation between the Employee Motivation scores and perceived level of Organizational Justice. There is a correlation, meaning that as one variable increased so did the other. An analysis of this table would show that as the Employee Motivation scores increase, so does the perceived level of organizational justice.

This means in organizations where employees are motivated, they are more likely to believe the company and its policies and procedures are fair, even if they do not always get what they want. Employees like to be treated fairly. That is, if a company's policies are fair and people are treated fairly, then the employees will be motivated to give their best efforts. If an employee feels the policies of an organization are unfair (i.e., due process is not observed), the employee has little motivation to give their best efforts in making their organization successful. Highly motivated employees are more likely to be rewarded with

promotion and healthy job satisfaction. Lowly motivated employees are more likely to be promoted, but are also less likely to be satisfied with the quality of their work.

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